

On the impossibility of non-trivial cycles and divergence in the Collatz Conjecture

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Introduction:

In the following document, I will try to demonstrate that the Collatz Conjecture is true using basic arithmetic tools. I say try due to the fact that this demonstration may have holes; thus, the reader is asked to be comprehensive to my situation: a young secondary student looking for guidance.

The Collatz Conjecture, also known as the “ $3x+1$ problem”, was posed by the German mathematician Lothar Collatz in the year 1937. In this conjecture, he proposed a sort of “game” in which he invites to pick any Natural number. If the number chosen was even, then it had to be divided by two, but, if it was odd, then it had to be multiplied by three and summed one. To the result of this operation, the same rules would be applied. The curious thing about this procedure, was that the numbers would always get stuck on the $4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$ cycle (which is known as the trivial cycle).

Let us take 11, for instance:

$$11 \rightarrow 3 * 11 + 1 = 34 \rightarrow 34/2 = 17 \rightarrow 3 * 17 + 1 = 52 \rightarrow 52/2 = 26 \rightarrow 26/2 = 13 \rightarrow 3 * 13 + 1 = 40 \rightarrow 40/2 = 20 \rightarrow 20/2 = 10 \rightarrow 10/2 = 5 \rightarrow 3 * 5 + 1 = 16 \rightarrow 16/2 = 8 \rightarrow 8/2 = 4$$

And that is how the cycle is reached.

The next challenge was to demonstrate it. For around 100 years, leading mathematicians have been trying to prove or refute this conjecture, through the use of various tools, such as “number trees” which showed the sequence from different numbers down to the trivial cycle, computational tests, or the Baker’s Theorem, which prove it to be true for unimaginably huge numbers.

These two last options are interesting, for the Conjecture has been verified for all the numbers less than 2^{71} , but mathematicians have not only been unsuccessful in calculating whether the numbers in between the ones verified and the proven by the Baker’s Theorem, get to the trivial cycle, but also to calculate the depth of the gap between these values.

This challenge has been an Odyssey, to which the mathematical community has faced, and this investigation looks forward to introducing a new perspective through the use of simpler tools than the usually employed for this problem.

The non-trivial cycles

My first approach was to find the equation of a cycle and, in order to do so, I developed the following method. Imagine to have the following sequence:

$$(3((3x + 1)/2) + 1)/8... = x$$

Which goes on, without knowing the exact times a number will be divided on the next step, but in the end, it will be equal to x, for it is a cycle we are talking about. It should be noted that a $3x+1$ operation can never be followed by another one, for this operation is applied only to odd numbers, which gives an even result, leading to the conclusion that a $3x+1$ will always be followed by a division by two. It is also important to note that after a division by two, many more may come, as seen in the example, where there are three divisions by two, represented by an eight, for $8 = 2^3$. To solve for x, the 2s on the denominator will be moved to the other side by multiplication, we will use the distributive property when a multiplication by 3 appears, which will affect an equation in parentheses and the '+1' terms that will eventually become a sum of powers of three, which we will then subtract from both sides of the equation to solve for x.

Formalizing:

May there be A_1 the power of the last division of 2, being the number divided by 2^{A_1} as the last step of the cycle. A_2 will be the power of the division before that, and A_3 before that and so on. "m" will be the value of the sum of every A_i . Each time a division by 2^{A_i} occurs, this value will be multiplied by both sides of the equation. Each time a $+ 3^k$ happens, where $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$, this number will be subtracted on both sides of the equation. In the end, it will look like this:

$$3^n x = 2^m x - N$$

Where n is the amount of multiplications by three, m is not the only the sum of every A_i , but also the divisions by two, and N is the result of summing the different powers of two and multiplied by the different A_i . Basing on this, we conclude that there are also n A_i terms.

It should be noted that the last step of the cycle is a division by two, for we assumed that x is odd, therefore, if the last step was a times three plus one operation, we would be left with an even number, which would contradict our initial assumption.

We can observe that N is the only number that is not multiplied by x, thus, we can subtract $2^m x$ and multiply both sides by minus one, in order to get the next equation:

$$2^m x - 3^n x = N$$

By factoring out x, we obtain:

$$x(2^m - 3^n) = N \Rightarrow x = \frac{N}{(2^m - 3^n)}$$

Due to the fact that N is a constant value determined by the sequence of the +1 operations in the cycle, it is a natural number, thus, $2^m - 3^n = D$ is a natural number as well, which means that $2^m > 3^n$. We can also conclude that $D|N$ because x is also a natural number, and, in order to maximize the possibilities of that happening (because in math, the worst possible case has always to be considered) m must be minimum, this is achieved by introducing logarithms to the equation:

$$2^m > 3^n \Rightarrow m > \log_2 3^n \Rightarrow m > n(\log_2 3) \approx 1,58n$$

And as it has to be minimum, we can express it as:

$m \approx n(\log_2 3)$ due to the fact that for big numbers, both expressions will be more and more alike, but never the same.

Now, to find the exact equation of N, we must understand that during the isolation of x process, A_1 will only affect x, thus, A_1 will not affect N. Then, it will be subtracted 1, then multiplied by 2^{A_2} , then subtracted by 3, multiplied by 2^{A_3} , subtracted 9 and so on.

May it be noted that will be repeated the same amount of times as $3x+1$ operations are, thus, the last step will be the subtraction of 3^n , and the multiplied by minus one, therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &\Rightarrow 2^{A_2} \Rightarrow 2^{A_2} + 3 \Rightarrow 2^{A_2+A_3} + 2^{A_3} * 3 + 3^2 \Rightarrow \dots \Rightarrow \\ &\Rightarrow 2^{A_2+A_3+\dots+A_n} + 2^{A_3+A_4+\dots+A_n} * 3 + 2^{A_4+A_5+\dots+A_n} * 3^2 + \dots + 2^{A_n} * 3^{n-1} + 3^n = N \end{aligned}$$

To demonstrate that the non-trivial cycles do not exist, it has to be proven that D does not divide $N \forall n > 1$.

In order to do so, we will use 2-adic valuation:

Let us rewrite the equation as:

$$\begin{aligned} x * D = N &\Rightarrow 2^m x - 3^n x = N \Rightarrow \\ &\Rightarrow 2^m x = 3^n x + 3^n + 2^{A_n} * 3^{n-1} + 2^{A_{n-1}+A_n} * 3^{n-2} + \dots + 2^{A_3+A_4+\dots+A_n} * 3^1 + 2^{A_2+A_3+\dots+A_n} = \\ &= 3^n(x + 1) + (2^{A_n} * 3^{n-1} + 2^{A_{n-1}+A_n} * 3^{n-2} + \dots + 2^{A_3+A_4+\dots+A_n} * 3^1 + 2^{A_2+A_3+\dots+A_n}) = 3^n(x + 1) + N_{sum} \end{aligned}$$

Where N_{sum} represents the sum of powers of two that conforms N. This is the equation that we will analyze with the 2-adic valuation, in other words, $v_2(LHS) \wedge v_2(RHS)$, where LHS represents the left side of the equation ($2^m x$), while RHS represents the right side of the equation ($3^n(x + 1) + N_{sum}$).

As x is odd, $v_2(LHS) = v_2(2^m) = m$. Next, we will evaluate the 2-adic valuation of RHS. In order to do so, we will analyze separately N_{sum} and the term $3^n(x + 1)$. To begin with, being the 2-adic valuation different for every power of two, to find the 2-adic valuation of N_{sum} , we have to find its minimum power. Being every A_i natural numbers as well, we may confirm that $A_n < A_n + k$, being k the next power or the sum of the following powers. Therefore, we conclude that A_n is the minimum, thus, $v_2(N_{sum}) = v_2(3^{n-1} * 2^{A_n}) = v_2(2^{A_n}) = A_n$. While analyzing the other term, we

must notice that, no matter the value of n natural, multiplying an odd number (3^n) by an even number (x+1); the valuation will depend on x+1.

Therefore, we conclude that $v_2(LHS) = m = v_2(RHS) = \min(v_2(x + 1), A_n)$. Let us analyze these cases separately.

If $v_2(x + 1) > A_n \Rightarrow v_2(RHS) = A_n = m$. But we know that m is the sum of every

$A_i \Rightarrow m > A_n \Rightarrow m \neq A_n \Rightarrow \rightarrow \leftarrow \Leftrightarrow n \geq 2$ due to the fact that if n equals 1, the so does m; but being n equal to 1, means that the only solution through this assumption is the trivial cycle.

That means that $v_2(RHS) = v_2(x + 1) = m$.

If $v_2(x + 1) = m \wedge m > A_n \Rightarrow v_2(x + 1) > A_n$

Therefore $\min(v_2(x + 1), A_n) \neq v_2(x + 1)$.

Finally, the only remaining case is $v_2(x + 1) = A_n$. The consequences of assuming this equation as true are unpredictable for RHS, nonetheless, recalling to the time we named the A_i and due to how the Collatz cycle is built, we can see that $v_2(3x + 1) = A_n$ where $3x+1$ is the first iteration of the cycle (let us remember that the A_i were named backwards, in order to, during the isolation of x , the first term to go to the other side was A_1).

Thus, for this third case, we assume that $v_2(x + 1) = v_2(3x + 1)$. Therefore, in order to discard the possibility of existence of non trivial cycles, we must prove this last assumption to be false.

With the objective of achieving it, $\exists q \in \mathbb{N}/x + 1 = 2^{A_n} * q$ with q an odd number.

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow x &= 2^{A_n} * q - 1 \Rightarrow 3x + 1 = 3(2^{A_n} * q - 1) + 1 = 3 * 2^{A_n} * q - 3 + 1 = 3 * 2^{A_n} * q - 2 = \\ &= 2(3 * 2^{A_n-1} * q - 1) \Rightarrow v_2(3x + 1) = v_2(2(3 * 2^{A_n-1} * q - 1)) = v_2(2) + v_2(3 * 2^{A_n-1} * q - 1) = \\ &= 1 + v_2(3 * 2^{A_n-1} * q - 1) = v_2(x + 1) = A_n = 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{If } A_n = 1 \Rightarrow 1 + v_2(3 * 2^{1-1} * q - 1) = 1 \Rightarrow 1 + v_2(3q - 1) = 1$$

As q and 3 are odd, by subtracting 1 to its multiplication, it becomes even

$$\Rightarrow v_2(3 * q - 1) \geq 1 \Rightarrow 1 + v_2(3 * q - 1) \geq 2 \neq A_n \Rightarrow \leftarrow$$

If $A_n > 1 \Rightarrow 3 * 2^{A_n-1} * q$ is even and subtracting one from it, turns it into an odd number

$$\Rightarrow v_2(3 * 2^{A_n-1} * q - 1) = 0 \Rightarrow v_2(3x + 1) = 1 \neq A_n \text{ because we have assumed that } A_n \geq 2.$$

Hence, there is a contradiction that this equation has no integer solution, apart from the one presented with the trivial cycle characteristics. Nonetheless, to finally discard non-trivial cycles we must prove that this contradiction still applies for every possible value of m . Let us define $R \in \mathbb{N}$ as the number summed to m when m is minimum. To continue the demonstration, we must prove that no matter the value of R , the logic applied still works.

Knowing now that the sum of every $A_i = m + R$, not only D increases its value, but so does N .

To still prove that D does not divide N , we must focus on the 2-adic valuation done and see if it still works.

We had 3 cases:

1. $v_2(x + 1) > A_n \Rightarrow v_2(RHS) = A_n < m + R$ and even if the increase "fell" right into A_n ;
 $A_n + R < m + R$
2. $v_2(x + 1) < A_n \Rightarrow v_2(RHS) = v_2(x + 1) = m + R$ but, if this is true, then
 $v_2(x + 1) > A_n + R > A_n$
3. $v_2(x + 1) = A_n$ which stays the same unless R "fell" right into A_n because, if
 $v_2(x + 1) = A_n + R \Rightarrow v_2(3x + 1) = A_n + R$ because the divisions by two would increase after the first $3x+1$ operation

Thus, we prove that the non-trivial cycles are impossible

The divergence to infinity

For a complete demonstration of the conjecture, it would not only be needed to be proven that non-trivial cycles do not exist, but also that a sequence that diverges to infinity does not exist. To analyze this situation, I thought of "tracking" the path of a number, basing on its congruence with powers of two in the following way:

By starting with an x number, we know that if x is even, it will be divided by two, but if it is odd, then it will be multiplied by 3 and summed 1.

Formalizing:

$$x \equiv 0(\text{mod } 2) \Rightarrow x/2$$

$$x \equiv 1(\text{mod } 2) \Rightarrow (3x + 1)/2$$

We will call this cases E (even) and O (odd) respectively

Afterwards, what happens with E?

Well, if the result is even then it will be divided by two, but if it is odd, then it will be multiplied by three, summed one and then it will be divided by two (Because after a $3x+1$ operation, the result will be even), but, is there any way to know what the next step will be, just knowing the first number?

There actually is. If $x \equiv 0(\text{mod } 4)$ then the result will be even, but, if $x \equiv 2(\text{mod } 4)$, then the result will be odd. Analyzing the congruence on base 4, we have 4 results:

$\equiv 0(\text{mod } 4)$; $\equiv 1(\text{mod } 4)$; $\equiv 2(\text{mod } 4)$; $\equiv 3(\text{mod } 4)$. As for E case, we assumed that x is even, analyzing the congruence by 4, we are left with $\equiv 0(\text{mod } 4) \vee \equiv 2(\text{mod } 4)$, while, in case O, we are left with $\equiv 1(\text{mod } 4) \vee \equiv 3(\text{mod } 4)$. Let us evaluate both possibilities:

$$x \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4) \Rightarrow 3x + 1 \equiv 3 * 1 + 1(\text{mod } 4) \Rightarrow 3x + 1 \equiv 4(\text{mod } 4) \Rightarrow 3x + 1 \equiv 0(\text{mod } 4)$$

Which means that after the eventual division by two, another one comes.

Now the other possibility:

$$x \equiv 3(\text{mod } 4) \Rightarrow 3x + 1 \equiv 3 * 3 + 1(\text{mod } 4) \Rightarrow 3x + 1 \equiv 10(\text{mod } 4) \Rightarrow 3x + 1 \equiv 2(\text{mod } 4)$$

Which means that after the eventual division by two, a $3x+1$ operation comes.

Thus, we divide the odd numbers in two groups:

$$x = 4z + 1 \vee x = 4z + 3$$

In order to clarify the idea of a Collatz iteration, we will define a Collatz function $f(x)$ the following way:

$$\exists f(x)/f(x) = x/2 \text{ if } x \text{ is even } \vee f(x) = \frac{3x+1}{2} \text{ if } x \text{ is odd}$$

Our goal is to prove that, given a random x , we can predict the long-term behaviour of $f(f(f(f(\dots f(x))))\dots)$.

The use of $f(x)$ will be considered an iteration and the first number will be x_0 with the purpose of writing the sequence as: $f(x_0) = x_1$; $f(f(x_0)) = f(x_1) = x_2$ and so on.

Returning to the cycle equation that had been made to prove the inexistence of non-trivial cycles, we may use x_0 as a starting point, and equal it to x_k (being k the amount of iterations, which will tend to infinite); trying to prove that x_k has to be 1 and not infinite (Due to the fact that every other possibility have been discarded by proving the inexistence of the non-trivial cycles); the we are left with equation as:

$$2^m x_k - 3^n x_0 = N \Rightarrow 2^m x_k = 3^n x_0 + N \Rightarrow x_k = \frac{3^n}{2^m} x_0 + \frac{N}{2^m}$$

In order for the divergence, $\frac{3^n}{2^m} > 1$ and for that for happening $1,58n \approx n \log_2 3 > m$.

We know that the total amount of iterations is k and there are two types of iterations:

1. $f(x_i)$ when x_i is odd (Case O)
2. $f(x_i)$ when x_i is even (Case E)

The sum of Cases O plus Cases E is k.

As there are a total of $n \cdot 3x+1$ operations, (that then lead to an eventual division by two) and that is the definition of Caso O, then we conclude that there are n Cases O.

On the other hand, there are a total of m divisions by two: some of them being from Cases O and some of the coming from Cases E; so, in order to find the real amount of divisions by two from Cases E, we must subtract the amount of Cases O from the total.

By multiplying the amount of division by two by Case, by the total of Cases O, we will have the amount of division by two from Cases O. Knowing that each Case O carries just one division by two, and that are n Cases O, the calculation we must do is: $1 * n = n$, therefore, the amount of Cases E is $m - n$.

Knowing that:

$$k = \text{Cases E} + \text{Cases O}$$

We can replace on the equation the amount of Cases:

$$k = (m - n) + n = m$$

This proves that the amount of division by two (m), equals the amount of iterations (k), while the amount of $3x+1$ operations (n) will always be equal or less than m.

Nonetheless, this might still happen: $1,58n > m > n$

To close this gap, we can think of a number, to which repeatedly applied $f(x)$, gives a large chain of Cases O. As it was detailed at the beginning of the section, we had classified the odd number in two groups: those which lead to another Case O ($4k+3$) or those which lead to a Case E ($4k+1$). We know that the lasts force the sequence to a reduction, but, how about the firsts ones? What if a sequence keeps itself in a large chain of Cases O?

For this to happen, the starting number (x_0) must accomplish with congruence conditions each time bigger:

- $f(x_0) = \text{Case O} \Leftrightarrow x_0 \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$
- $f(f(x_0)) = \text{Case O} \Leftrightarrow x_0 \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$
- $f(f(f(x_0))) = \text{Case O} \Leftrightarrow x_0 \equiv 15 \pmod{16}$

For this process, for the number to have a k Cases O chain, the starting number x_0 must accomplish a condition of the way:

$$x_0 \equiv c_\infty \pmod{2^\infty}$$

Where c_k is a specific constant that depends on the value of k.

Therefore, in order for this to happen, the remainder would have to be infinitely big, so that k tends to infinite; but being x_0 a natural number, it can not have an infinite remainder, which

generates a contradiction that makes the sequence fall on a Case E.

Due to the inevitability of falling on a Case E, keeping on a Case E chain, becomes more and more inevitable, thus, it comes a moment in the sequence for a determined k where $m > 1,58n$.

Now, let us assume that there is a set of numbers that diverge to infinity, by the minimum principle, there is a least element.

Due to the analysis done, we can conclude that there is a point where a number smaller than the starter one is reached, and, by applying the minimum principle, we get to a contradiction, because a number smaller than the minimum that diverges, converges.

Therefore, we discard divergence.

Conclusions:

This demonstration establishes that the non-trivial cycles and the divergence, are mathematical, logical and irrefutably impossible. By being this the only two cases that may contend a counter-example, we then conclude it to be true. By representing the Collatz cycles as the equation $x * D = N$, it became easier to refute the non-trivial cycles, by proving that the only solution had the trivial cycle's characteristics, through a 2-adic valuation.

On the other hand, by understanding how the modular information from the initial number is transmitted to the following iterations, it was possible to understand why the reduction is inevitable, which contradicts the divergence to infinity given the Principle of the Minimum. Unlike other demonstrations and research, I was conditioned by the limited knowledge due to my young age to use simpler tools than those generally used to address this problem; focusing on an exhaustive modular analysis instead of large-scale computational tests or the use of more complex tools like Baker's Theorem.

Finally, the resolution of this problem provides a deeper understanding of sequences that include addition, multiplication, division, and even subtraction, indirectly, the 4 most basic operations of arithmetic, which have been shown to have more complex nuances than is commonly believed.

In addition to this, by combining this demonstration with other mathematicians' works on the Conjecture, any hypothesis that has been raised to prove the problem, which is true if and only if the Conjecture was correct, is automatically demonstrated; therefore, not only could the procedures I used inspire new research, but also the conclusions of other mathematicians, indirectly proven through this document.

Acknowledgments

I believe that due to my young age (18 years old, but 16 at its beginning), I was limited to using simpler tools than those possessed by professional mathematicians. Therefore, the originality of my contribution was based on the fact that I did not use complex tools, as I do not yet fully understand them.

Furthermore, this document would not have been possible without the help of Gemini, an Artificial Intelligence model developed by Google, to which I entrusted the task of listing simple tools I could use to continue with my proof when I didn't know how to proceed; support on the translation of technical words from Spanish to English; and to perform the heaviest calculations in terms of quantity, repetitiveness, and simplicity, such as the creation of a table of 32 mod reminders, which was later discarded. Although it had several errors, it was easier to correct these calculations than to perform them myself.